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Data management plan (DMP)

Algorithms performance comparison in a classification task

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1.0	2023-04-23	Final version of DMP

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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	final_comparison_all_acc	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P2	final_comparison_all_mse	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P3	knn_comparison_acc	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P4	knn_comparison_mse	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P5	rfr_comparison_acc	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P6	rfr_comparison_mse	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P7	nn_comparison_acc	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P8	nn_comparison_mse	Output barchart	png	30kB	No
P9	nn_best_training_mse	Output plot	png	30kB	No
P10	nn_scaled_best_training_mse	Output plot	png	30kB	No
P11	final_comparison	Output plot	png	30kB	No
P12	abalone_cleaned	Modified input data	csv	210kB	No

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Abalone Age	https://www.openml.org/d/44956	CC BY 4.0	no
R2	in-vehicle coupon recommendation	https://archive-beta.ics.uci.edu/dataset/603/in+vehicle+coupon+recommendation	CC BY 4.0	no
R3	Code repository	https://github.com/askimos/predictions_abalone_invehicle	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7935048 License: MIT	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

How will the research data be generated or reused and which methods and software will be used?

Data comes from an original (non-machine-learning) study: Warwick J Nash, Tracy L Sellers, Simon R Talbot, Andrew J Cawthorn and Wes B Ford (1994) "The Population Biology of Abalone (*Haliotis* species) in Tasmania. I. Blacklip Abalone (*H. rubra*) from the North Coast and Islands of Bass Strait", Sea Fisheries Division, Technical Report No. 48 (ISSN 1034-3288)

It is not planned that new data is being collected.

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The input and output data can be found in the directory data. All datasets can be used according the specified license.

The source code itself can be used and adapted for further experiments.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

To track changes of data, code and structure, git will be used. The project is available under https://github.com/askimos/predictions_abalone_invehicle.

The metadata provided for the data is the information about the presence of missing values and basic description of attributes. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

A far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Metadata to the data sets will be available in github, where it will be shortly described in the README and information is given on how and where to download the files. The produced data will also be shortly described in the README file of the project, useful links are given to understand the retrieved

data so that people who like to reuse the data can have a basic understanding. As this documentation is on the GitHub repository, it can be accessed with the code and data in the repository

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: check of logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project coordinator. A public github repository will be accessible.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	license
P1	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P2	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P3	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P4	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P5	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P6	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P7	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P8	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P9	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P10	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P11	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	CC BY 4.0
P12	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-15	10.5281/zenodo.7935019	CC BY 4.0

The repository used in this project is Github. It is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and

mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com> Specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data: Using this data a machine running python 3.9.13 is required. Further instructions on how to run the experiments are explained in the Readme.md file in the repository.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P2	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P3	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P4	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P5	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P6	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P7	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P8	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P9	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P10	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P11	10.5281/zenodo.7934999	15 years	People interested in ecology or human behaviour.
P12	10.5281/zenodo.7935019	15 years	People interested in ecology, especially sea organisms.
R3	10.5281/zenodo.7935048	15 years	The target audience are students and the general public because this experiment is illustrating the use of a DMP in a small software project.

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Maciej Miksa will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.